

AN ANALYTICAL METHOD TO PREDICT STIFFENER DEBONDING IN POSTBUCKLED COMPRESSION PANELS

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Postbuckled skins with bonded skin-stiffener joints

- Structurally efficient (joints and postbuckled design)
- Reduced tooling
- But certification* requires
 - repeatable manufacture
 - quantification of uncertainty
 - efficient and accurate models

Postbuckled
fuselage skin
EU “STUNNING”
project

Overview

- FEA models for skin-stiffener debonding
- Strip model – buckling and debonding
- Results – Strip vs FEA (Cohesive Zone and Virtual Crack Closure)
- Conclusions & Future Work

Modelling of postbuckled bonded joints

- **Cohesive zones (CZM)**
 - Energy, **stiffness** and **strength** required
 - Accuracy dependent on mesh size
 - Mixed mode criterion

Both computationally costly; mesh dependent with mixed mode criterion

- **Virtual crack closure (VCCT)**
 - Energy to close crack
 - Mixed mode criterion

We propose a meshless Strip method with Mode I criterion

Strip method for buckling analysis

- Solves strong form of plate element equilibrium equations (Wittrick and Williams, 1974)
- Models any prismatic stiffened panel
- Buckling modes are periodic and sinusoidal with half-wavelength λ
- Requires one strip element per laminated plate

Strip model for skin-flange debonding

- Debonding releases bending energy as local (periodic) buckling mode relaxes
- Strain energy U released during debonding of area A_d dependent on buckling strain ε^C

$$G = \frac{\partial U}{\partial A_d} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon^C} \frac{\partial \varepsilon^C}{\partial A_d} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon^C} \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon^C}{f(x) \partial b} \right) \left(\frac{f(x) \partial b}{\partial A_d} \right) = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon^C} \frac{\partial \varepsilon^C}{\partial b} \frac{\partial b}{\partial A_d}$$

b is debonding strip width; $f(x)$ defines debond shape in axial x direction

Strip model for skin-flange debonding – $\frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon^C}$

Total axial strain energy over full wavelength 2λ

$$U = U_1 + U_2 = 2EA\lambda \left[\left(\frac{\varepsilon^C}{2}\right)^2 + \varepsilon^C(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) + \frac{r}{2}(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C)^2 \right]$$

Hence

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon^C} = 2EA\lambda(1 - r)(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C)$$

Strip model for skin-stiffener debonding – Buckling sensitivity

Assume strip delamination over opening half-wave $\partial A_d = \lambda \partial b$

$$G = \frac{\partial U}{\partial A_d} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varepsilon^C} \frac{\partial \varepsilon^C}{\partial b} \frac{\partial b}{\partial A_d} = 2EA (1 - r)(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^C) \frac{\partial \varepsilon^C}{\partial b}$$

In terms of applied load, accounting for post-buckled stiffness

$$G = \frac{2}{EA} (1 - r)(P - P^C) \frac{\partial P^C}{\partial b}$$

Energy released axially, due to bending and orthogonal to damage growth (no crack driving force).

Hence, we assume Mode I

$$P_{init} = P^C + \frac{G_{1C}EA}{2(1 - r) \frac{\partial P^C}{\partial b}}$$

where $\frac{\partial P^C}{\partial b}$ are calculated from
Butler and Williams, 1992.

Results - Post-buckled skin-flange panel

Example problem

Laminates

- Skin $[\pm 45/0/90/0_3/\pm 45/0_2/\overline{90}]_S$
- Flange $[\pm 45/0/90/0_3/\pm 45/0_2/\overline{90}]_S$
- HexPly® IM7/8552 (CF/epoxy)

Two **bonding** options

1. Welded; $G_{1c} = 1083 \text{ J/m}^2$; two 250 μm thick thermoplastic polyetherimide (PEI) films*
2. Co-cured $G_{1c} = 277 \text{ J/m}^2$

*Maierhofer, Loukaides, Carr, Bisagni, & Butlér, 2024

Results - Post-buckled skin-stiffener panel models

- **FEA model (CZM)**
 - 8-node shell with cohesive interfaces
 - 0.5mm mesh in region of delamination
 - Cohesive ply interfaces in flange above bond surface
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- **Strip model**
 - Three strips: flange with skin below flange, exposed skin and unbonded flange
 - Sensitivities $\frac{\partial P^C}{\partial b_2}$ for exposed skin; constant panel volume

Results - buckling and debonding loads

- Weld (PEI) strength reduced for 0.5mm FE mesh (Turon et al, 2007)
- Co-cured result 2% CZM Strip difference
- Welded debond: CZM 9% below Strip load
- CZM would need bi-linear softening to model thermoplastic stress-strain
- Strip uses only SERR

Results - Post-buckled skin-hat stiffener bond strength*

- Welded thermoplastic laminates (T700/LM-PAEK)
- Axial compressed 3-stiffener panel
- Test and FEA (Virtual Crack Closure)

Results - Post-buckled skin-hat stiffener bond strength

	Test*	VCCT*	Strip
Debond load P_{d2} (kN)	316	320	309

- Debond occurs under hat
- Strip result within 3% of Test and VCCT

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Conclusions

- Thermoplastic weld – increases co-cured joint strength by 50%
- New Strip method
 - Requires stable (piecewise linear) post-buckling
 - No mesh to model localisation
 - Solution in seconds c.f. FEA hours (up to 10^7 times slower)
 - More accurate than Cohesive Zone Model in FEA for thermoplastic
 - Good agreement with VCCT and experimental test
 - General – potential for application using alternative buckling models